

ASSESSMENT OF WOMEN RICE FARMERS PARTICIPATION IN FARMER MONI PROGRAMME IN NASSARAWA STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the participation of women rice farmers in the Farmer Moni Programme in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 306 respondents for the study. Data were collected using a questionnaire and the data collected were analyzed by employing both descriptive, multiple regression, and paired t-test statistics. The result of the socio-economic characteristics of the women farmers shows that the majority (66.7%) of them were married. The average household size of the farmers was 6, while their average age was 39. The study further revealed that the women farmers had an average of 11 years of farming experience while the majority (78.3%) of them had formal education. The average farm size of the farmers was 1.9 hectares, and their average annual income was N470,846.55. Most (54.0%) of the farmers had at least 5 contacts with extension agents within the year. The study further revealed that the women farmers received an average of N381,868.13 from the Farmer Moni programme. The study showed that most (42.1%) of the respondents believed that the participation of women farmers in the programme was high. The regression analysis shows that educational level, farming experience, farm size, and income significantly influenced the participation of women farmers in the Farmer Moni programme. It was recommended that Implementers of the Farmer Moni Programme should provide targeted financial literacy training to ensure proper utilization of funds.

Keywords: *women farmers, farmer moni, rice farmers*

INTRODUCTION

Women's farmer empowerment entails enhancing their spiritual, political, social, educational, and economic strength in commodities and their political standing, particularly those who have been historically marginalized in society (Shettar, 2015). This process involves protecting women farmers from all forms of discrimination and violence. Women farmer empowerment aims to cultivate a

society and political environment where women can thrive without the fear of discrimination, oppression, exploitation and the pervasive sense of persecution associated with being a woman in a traditionally male-dominated framework (Shettar, 2015). In recent years, efforts to boost agricultural productivity and ensure the inclusion of smallholder farmers, particularly women, have been prioritized by policymakers and

development organizations (Ahmed, Rahman, Farouque, Sarker and Sojib, 2022). This is evident in initiatives like the Farmer Moni Programme, a microcredit scheme designed to empower rural farmers, including women, with financial resources and skills for improved agricultural productivity. The Farmer Moni Programme, introduced by the Federal Government of Nigeria under the Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP), aims to address these challenges by providing interest-free loans and capacity-building support to smallholder farmers, including women, to enhance their agricultural and entrepreneurial activities (Eranga, 2020). Agricultural production has been a dominant issue of discussion in national economic development of Nigeria. Most food crops produced in the country come from the efforts of the rural farmers who depend largely on traditional farming systems (Nsoanya and Nenna, 2011). The agricultural sector remains amongst the most important sectors in the economy of any country. It is a known fact that Agriculture provides 70% of the employment in the country (Nkonya and Philips, 2009). The industry is undergoing a shift due to increased commercial activity across small, medium, and large enterprises. Nigeria's agricultural sector holds significant importance for the economy, serving as a crucial provider of food, contributing to the gross domestic product (GDP), generating employment opportunities, supplying raw materials for agro-allied industries, and generating foreign earnings (Nkonya and Philips, 2009). The main objective of the study is to assess the participation of women rice farmers in the Farmer Moni Programme in Nasarawa State, Nigeria, while the specific

objectives are to:

- i. describe the socio-economic characteristics of women rice farmers participating in the Farmer Moni Programme in Nasarawa State.
 - ii. determine the average amount of finance accessed by women rice farmers who participated in the Farmer Moni Programme in the study area.
 - iii. determine the level of participation of women rice farmers in the Farmer Moni Programme in the study area.
- analyse the socio-economic factors influencing women rice farmers' extent of participation in the Farmer Moni Programme.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

The study was carried out in Nasarawa State. Nasarawa State is bordered in the north by Kaduna State, in the west by the Federal Capital Territory (Abuja), in the south by the states of Kogi and Benue, and in the east by the states of Taraba and Plateau. The State, which is located in the Southern Guinea Savanna zone of the nation, has a total land area of 28,735 square kilometres and a population of 2,679,433 (Idu, Fadiji and Evinemi, 2020). With a variety of cash crops produced throughout the year, agriculture serves as the foundation of the economy of Nasarawa State. With the bulk of the population actively engaged in farming, the State is primarily an agrarian society. Aside from rice, the research region also produces yam, beniseed, sorghum, melon, cassava, cowpea, and maize as food crops.

2.2 Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was used to sample respondents for the study. The

first stage involved the purposive selection of two (2) agricultural zones from the state. The selected zones were rice production areas. For the second stage, three (3) blocks were chosen from each of the zones, which resulted in six (6) blocks. Three (3) cells were selected from each of the blocks, which resulted in a total of eighteen (18) cells. Finally, from each of the cells seventeen (17) respondents were selected. The total number of the respondents for the study was 306.

2.3 Data Collection and Analysis

The study relied on primary data collected through a meticulously crafted questionnaire. The administration of this questionnaire was facilitated by the researcher along with proficient ADP enumerators who possess a deep understanding of the local context. Objective i, ii, iii, iv, v, vi and viii were achieved using descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, and percentage, while objective vii were actualized using logistic regression analysis.

2.4 Model Specification: Multiple Regression Regression analysis involves estimating the parameters of a regression model to describe the relationship between the dependent variable (Y) and one or more independent variables (X).

- X₄ = marital status, (single =1, married = 2, widowed = 3, divorced = 4)
- X₅ = household size (measured by the number of people living under one roof)
- X₆ = Farm size (measured in hectares)
- X₇ = Farming experience (measured in years)
- X₈ = Income (measured in Naira)
- X₉ = Membership of association (yes = 1, otherwise = 0)
- X₁₀ = Access to extension services (number of extension contacts per cropping season)
- μ = error term

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Socio-Economic Characteristics of Women Rice Farmers

The result in Table 1 revealed that the majority (66.7%) of the women rice farmers were married, indicating that rice farming is largely undertaken by women within family settings. Single women (25.7%) also form a considerable proportion, suggesting some level of independence in farming. Divorced (6.0%) and widowed (1.7%) women make up a smaller percentage, potentially highlighting the challenges faced by women in farming without spousal support. Married women may have better access to labor through family members, but their decision-making power in farming activities could be influenced by their spouses (Douanghachanh *et al.*, 2021).

$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + \dots$ The study shows that 55.6% of the farmers

$+ b_{10}\mu$ Equation (1)

- Where:
- Y = level of participation in Farmer Moni Programme (1 = low, 2 = middle, 3 = high)
- a = constant term
- b₁ – b₁₀ = regression coefficients to be estimated
- X₁ = age: (will be measured in years)
- X₂ = gender; (male = 1, female = 0)
- X₃ = education; (total number of years spent in formal education)

have a household size consisting of at most 5 persons, and this indicates smaller families; 24.7% have 6-10 members, while 13.9% had a household size of more than 10 persons. The average household size of the farmers is 6 members. Larger households may provide more family labour for rice farming, reducing the cost of hired labor (Foster and Rosenzweig, 2022). However, they may also have higher consumption needs, affecting reinvestment in farming. Table 1 further shows that the average age

of the farmers is 39 years. Most farmers (37.3%) are between 31–40 years old, followed closely by 41–50 years (36.4%). Younger farmers (21–30 years) make up 20.1%, while only 6.4% are above 50 years. The predominance of farmers in their productive years (31–50 years) suggests that rice farming is dominated by economically active individuals. The presence of younger farmers indicates some level of youth participation, which is promising for sustainability.

Also, 57.4% of the farmers had at most 10 years of experience, indicating a significant number of relatively new entrants. About 40.6% have 11–20 years, suggesting a good mix of experienced farmers. Only 2% have more than 20 years of experience. The average farming experience is 11 years. Many farmers are still in the early to mid-stages of their farming careers, meaning they may still be learning and adapting to better rice farming techniques.

The educational qualification of the respondents revealed that 34.7% have post-secondary education, suggesting a significant presence of educated women in rice farming in the study area. About 29.0% attained secondary education, and 14.7% have primary education. Those who had no formal education accounted for 21.7% of the respondents, indicating a potential barrier to information access. Higher education levels among farmers can positively impact the adoption of modern farming techniques and improved technology Addai, Temoso and Ng'ombe, 2022).

The study revealed that 72% of women farm on small plots (1-3 hectares), while only 14.8% cultivate less than 1 hectare. Only 3.9% cultivate more than 7 hectares, showing that large-scale women farmers are rare. The average farm size is 1.9 hectares. Most women are smallholder farmers, which may limit economies of scale and profitability. Table 1 further reveals that most (59%) of the women farmers earn between N100,001–500,000, while 31.4% earn between N500,001–1,000,000. Only 3.3% earn above N1,000,000, showing that very few women make high profits. 3% earn below N100,000, indicating the presence of extremely low-income earners among the farmers. The average annual income is N470,846.55. Although most women are within the medium-income category, relatively few earn high incomes, suggesting challenges such as low productivity, lack of access to inputs, and poor market linkages.

The study revealed that 54.0% of the women had five or more extension visits, indicating strong extension service coverage. Around 29.0% had four visits, meaning most farmers had access to agricultural information. Only 11.3% had two visits and 5.7% had three visits. Regular extension contact enhances knowledge transfer and the adoption of improved rice farming practices (Camphenhout, 2021). However, the 17% of farmers receiving less than four visits may not be getting adequate support.

Table 1: Socio-economic Characteristics of Women Rice Farmers

Variables	Frequency	Percent	Mean
Marital Status			
Married	200	66.7	
Single	77	25.7	
Divorced	18	6.0	
Widowed	5	1.7	
Household Size			
= 5	167	55.6	
6–10	74	24.7	6
11 – 15	38	12.6	
=15	4	1.3	
Age			
21 – 30	60	20.1	
31 – 40	112	37.3	39
41 – 50	109	36.4	
=51	19	6.4	
Years of Rice Farming Experience			
=10 11 – 20	172	57.4	
21 – 30	122	40.6	11
	6	2	
Edu No formal education			
Primary school	65	21.7	
Secondary school	44	14.7	
Post-secondary school	44	14.7	
Farm Size <1 1-3			
4-6	87	29.0	
=7	104	34.7	
Income =100,000 100,001-			
500,000 500,001-1,000,000	44	14.8	
>1,000,000	216	72	1.9
Extension Contacts	28	9.3	
No visit 2 3 4 =5	12	3.9	
<i>Source: Field Survey, 2025</i>			
	9	3	
	177	59	470846.55
	94	31.4	
	10	3.3	
	34	11.3	
	17	5.7	
	87	29.0	
	162	54.0	

3.2 Amount Received from Farmer Moni Programme

Table 2 presents the distribution of the amounts received by women farmers from the Farmer Moni Programme, along with their frequencies and percentages. The majority (70.4%) of beneficiaries received more than ₦300,000. This suggests that most participants were able to access substantial financial support, which could contribute to improved farming activities, purchase of inputs, or expansion of farm operations. This indicates that the programme was largely effective in disbursing relatively large amounts to women farmers. In their study on the importance of agricultural credit, Balana and Oyeyemi (2022) opined that government interventions such as Farmer Moni have helped in providing some level of financing for rural women. About 23.1% of the participants received between ₦100,000 and ₦300,000. This group represents those who may have had access to funding but at a lower scale compared to

the majority. The variation in disbursement amounts may be due to differences in farm sizes, repayment history, financial needs, or eligibility criteria set by the Farmer Moni Programme. Millions (2012) revealed that factors such as family size, farm size and loan repayment time influence the amount of loan farmers are able to access. Those who received ₦100,000 or less accounted for 6.6% of the beneficiaries, indicating that a small fraction of participants accessed minimal financial support. This may suggest limitations in eligibility, incomplete applications, or lesser creditworthiness of some women farmers. The mean amount received is ₦381,868.13, indicating that, on average, beneficiaries received this amount through the programme. This is an encouraging sign as it implies that the Farmer Moni Programme was able to provide meaningful financial support to women farmers, helping them make impactful investments in their agricultural activities (Michael-Olomu and Akah, 2024).

Table 2: Amount Received from Farmer Moni Programme

Amount	Frequency	Percent
≤100000	6	6.6
100000-300000	21	23.1
>300000	64	70.4
Mean	381868.13	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

3.3 Level of Participation of Women in Farmer Moni Programme

The result in Table 3 presents the level of participation of women farmers in the Farmer Moni Programme. The result shows that 42.1% stated that there was a high level of participation of women in the Farmer Moni programme. High participation may

be due to factors like better access to information, effective support systems, and greater commitment or interest in the benefits of the programme. Balana and Oyeyemi (2022) indicated that there is an increased level of participation of women in programmes such as the government's Farmer Moni, Market Moni and other

government economic empowerment programme. About 41.7% of respondents indicated that there was middle level of women participation while only 16.2% of the respondents had low participation. The participation distribution is relatively balanced, with a clear divide between low, middle, and high levels. The high and middle participation groups combined represent 83.8% of the sample.

that a significant majority of women farmers benefitted, to some extent, from the Farmer Moni Programme. Okolo-Obasi and Uduji (2024) revealed that there is more participation of urban women in the programme than rural women, and therefore, rural women should be afforded more opportunities to participate in the loan scheme.

Table 3: Level of Participation of Women Farmers in Farmer Moni Programme

Level of Participation	Frequency	Percentage
Low	47	16.2
Middle	121	41.7
High	122	42.1

Source: Field Survey, 2025

3.4 Effect of Socio-Economic Characteristics of Women Farmers on Participation in Farmer Moni Programme

Table 4 presents the regression analysis results examining the impact of socio-economic factors on the participation of women farmers in the Farmer Moni Programme within the study area. The R² value of 0.481 indicates that 48.1% of the variations in the dependent variable (level of participation) are explained by the independent variables included in the model. This suggests that nearly half of the factors influencing participation are captured in the model, while the remaining 51.9% is due to error or unobserved variables not included in the regression. The F-statistic value of 7.024, which is significant at the 1% probability level, confirms that the overall model is statistically significant and appropriately specified. This means that the set of independent variables used in the model collectively influence participation in the Farmer Moni Programme. Farming experience is statistically significant at 1% and has a positive effect on participation in the Farmer Moni

Programme. This suggests that women with more years of farming experience are more likely to participate in the programme. Experienced farmers may have better knowledge of financial programmes, greater confidence in accessing credit, and improved ability to meet programme requirements (Reimer *et al.*, 2023). Education was found to have a positive and significant effect on participation, meaning that more educated women farmers are more likely to engage in the Farmer Moni Programme. Educated women may have better access to information, stronger financial management skills, and greater awareness of available opportunities. This is in line with the assertion of Geza *et al.* (2022) that education influences the participation of farmers in empowerment programmes. Farm size has a positive and significant effect on participation at 10% probability level, indicating that women with larger farms are slightly more likely to engage with the Farmer Moni Programme. This could be because women with larger farms require more financial support to sustain production and expansion, making them more inclined to seek funding

opportunities.

Income was also found to be positive and significantly related to participation in the Farmer Moni Programme. This suggests that women farmers with higher incomes are more likely to participate due to better

financial literacy, stronger financial stability, and easier access to complementary resources such as collateral or networks (Kayongo and Mathiassen, 2023).

Table 4: Regression Result of the Effect of Socio-Economic Characteristics of Women Farmers on their Participation in Farmer Moni Programme

Variables	B	Std.Error	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.177	.414	2.847	.005
Marital status	.035	.065	.537	.592
Household size	-.004	.015	-.300	.764
Age	-.001	.008	-.195	.845
Farming experience	.042	.011	3.922	.000***
Educational level	.082	.048	1.724	.086*
Farm size	.047	.026	1.836	.068*
Income	4.572E-007	.000	2.526	.012**
Extension contact	.036	.054	.659	.511

Dependent variable: level of participation, $f = (7.024, 0.000)$, $R^2 = 0.481$

***significant at 1%, *significant at 5%, ***significant at 10%*

Source: Field Survey, 2025

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study assessed the participation of women rice farmers in the Farmer Moni Programme in Nasarawa State and its impact on their productivity and livelihoods. The findings revealed that a significant proportion of the women farmers are married and operate within family structures, which may influence their decision-making and access to labor. The majority are smallholder farmers cultivating between 1–3 hectares, with limited access to large-scale production opportunities. Despite their active engagement in rice farming, most of them face constraints such as financial

limitations, inadequate market linkages, and challenges in accessing modern farming technologies.

Based on these findings, the study recommends the following:

1. Implementers of the Farmer Moni Programme should provide targeted financial literacy training to ensure proper utilization of funds.
2. There should be an improvement in extension services to increase the awareness and participation of women farmers in various government empowerment initiatives.

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